

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some Azoles and Azines

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Selenadiazole, pyrazole, quinoxaline and 1,2,3-triazines have been synthesised from *p*-diacetylbenzene and their biological activity has been evaluated.

THE wide spectrum biological activities¹ of azoles and azines prompted us to synthesise some new derivatives from *p*-diacetylbenzene with expected biological activity.

p-Diacetylbenzene (1) was condensed with semicarbazide hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine to yield the corresponding semicarbazone (2a) and phenylhydrazone (2b) respectively. The most widely used method for the synthesis of 1,2,3-selenadiazole involves the oxidative cyclisation of semicarbazones with selenium dioxide². Thus the semicarbazone (2a) was reacted with selenium dioxide in glacial acetic acid to yield an oxidative cyclised product, 1,2,3-selenadiazole (3). The formylation of the phenylhydrazone (2b) using Vilsmeier-Haak reagent³ (DMF/POCl₃) yielded the corresponding 4-formylpyrazole derivative (4).

The reaction of diacetylbenzene (1) with diethyl oxalate in presence of sodium ethoxide, provided diethyl terphthaloylpyruvate (5). Condensation of

ortho-diamino-compounds with α -keto-esters offers the pyrazine ring system. Thus, the condensation of 5 with *o*-phenylenediamine yielded the quinoxaline derivative (6). Basic hydrolysis of 6 gave 2-hydroxy-3-methylquinoxaline (7) and terphthalic acid. The reaction of 5 with semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide in refluxing acetic acid provided 1,2,4-triazine derivatives 8 and 9 respectively. Hydrazinolysis of 5 with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing acetic acid yielded ethyl pyrazole-3-carboxylate derivative (10) (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd.	M p. °C	Mol. formula	Mol. wt
2a	> 300	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂	276.16
3	165 (decomp.)	C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ Se ₂	339.98
4	274	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	418.40
5	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₈	362.30
6	> 300	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	450.18
8	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₆	384.13
9	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	416.10
10	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂	326.16

* ν_{\max} 3 840s (C-Se-N), 4 1 600s (C=N), 1 690s (CHO), 2 284w (CH aldehydic), 5 1 751s (CO), 1 730s (CO of CO₂C₂H₅), 6 1 640w (CO), 1 650s (CO), 3 200-3 300br (NH), 7 1 640w (CO), 1 650s (CO), 3 150-3 200br (NH), 9 1 715s (CO), 3 250s cm⁻¹ (NH).

δ (DMSO) 5: 1.4 (6H, t, 2CO₂CH₂CH₃), 2.75 (4H, s, 2CH₃), 4.3 (4H, q, 2CO₂CH₂CH₃), 7.1, 8.1 (4H, dd, ArH's); and δ (CDCl₃) 10: 1.4 (6H, t, 2CO₂CH₂CH₃), 4.4 (4H, q, 2CO₂CH₂CH₃), 7.75 (6H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, broad, NH).

Scheme 1

The antimicrobial activity of compounds 1, 2, 4–10 was tested against *Escherichia coli* NRRL B 210, *Bacillus mycoides* NCSR 531, *Bacillus subtilis* NRRL B 543 (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* NRRL Y 567 (yeast) using the disc-diffusion method. The results show that the *para*-diacetylbenzene derivatives (1, 2) possess no antimicrobial activity against these organisms but the introduction of heterocyclic moieties gives the *p*-diacetylbenzene derivatives a moderate antimicrobial activity (2 mm inhibition zones) for 4–10 against all the organisms.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Microanalysis were carried out at the Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian HA 100 (100 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p-Diacetylbenzene semicarbazone (2a): To a solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (1.5 g) in water (4 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The precipitate so obtained after cooling was filtered to give 2.

1,4-Bis(1,2,3-selenadiazolo-4-yl)benzene (3): To a solution of 2 (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) selenium dioxide powder (0.01 mol) was added. The mixture was warmed gently on a water-bath with stirring until the gas evolution ceased. The reaction mixture was then filtered, the solvent evaporated under the reduced pressure, and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid.

1,4-Bis(1-phenyl-5-formylpyrazol-5-yl)benzene (4): To phosphorus oxychloride (0.01 mol) cooled in an ice-water bath to 5°, dry dimethylformamide (10 ml) was added slowly with stirring over 15 minutes to yield a white precipitate. The reaction mixture was warmed gently to dissolve the precipitate and a clear solution was obtained. To it 3 was added in small portions with stirring over a period of 30–40 min and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 5 h to give a dark red-brown solution. It was poured in ice-water and the resulting colourless solid was crystallised from ethanol.

Diethyl terphthaloylpyruvate (5): To an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide (2.3 g sodium dissolved in 40 ml ethanol), a solution of *p*-diacetylbenzene (0.1 mol) and diethyl oxalate (0.1 mol) was slowly added with stirring. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystals.

2-Hydroxyquinoxaline (6): A mixture of 6 (0.01 mol) and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h. The resulting reddish brown solid was crystallised from acetic acid as reddish crystals.

5-Oxo-1,2,3-triazenes (8, 9): Following the above reaction conditions and using semicarbazide and/or thiosemicarbazide instead of *o*-phenylenediamine, the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystal of 8 and red crystals of 9.

Ethyl-pyrazol-3-carboxylate (10): A mixture of 5 (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in acetic acid (10 ml) was left at room temperature for 3 h and then refluxed for 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals.

Biological testing: The diffusion assay method was followed using media containing (g dm⁻³) peptone (6.0), yeast extract (3.0), meat extract (1.5), glucose (1.0) and agar (20.0). All ingredients were dissolved in distilled water (1 dm³) and adjusted to pH 6. The compound (0.01 g) was dissolved in chloroform (3 ml) and then 0.1 ml of the solution was tested for biological activity and the inhibition zone was measured.

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